

Legal Protection Of Auction Winner On Minutes Of Auction Canceled By Court (Case Study Decision No.31/Pdt.G/2015/PN.Jmb)

Nanda Fenta Saputra, Pujiyono, Arief Suryono

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 11, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Auction, Cancellation By Court, Legal Protection, Auction Winner</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5090739</p>	<p><i>In the case of an auction that is cancelled by the court, it is often considered that the aggrieved party is the debtor, but if you look at it from another point of view, the winner of the auction also bears the loss in terms of time, energy, and costs for the transfer of names and taxes. This article aims to discuss the legal protection of the auction winner for the auction cancelled by the court. This research uses normative juridical research. This research specification uses an analytical perspective type, namely research by knowing facts or actual conditions. Collecting research data using literature studies on primary law, secondary legal materials, and non-legal materials. The data analysis technique in this study is a prescriptive analysis using a statutory approach. Several articles that can be used by the auction winner to claim compensation for the minutes of the auction cancelled by the court are Article 1365, Article 1457, Article 1473, Article 1474, Article 1479, Article 1480, Article 1266, and Article 1267 of the Civil Code. This article concludes that there is a need for compensation to be given to the auction winner for the auction cancelled by the court, because just like the debtor who suffered losses due to the limit value being too low, the auction winner also suffered losses in terms of time, effort, and costs for the cancellation.</i></p>

Introduction

The banking sector has an important role in supporting national development, especially with the current trend of economic growth in the modern era causing the level of public consumption to be higher, but not everyone is able to fulfill it properly. So as a business entity, bank has a strategic position in economic activities. Apart from being a tool in setting monetary policy, bank is the main source of financing or credit for entrepreneurs and individuals. In order to improve the standard of living in this globalization era, the government seeks to encourage the ease of public investment/business. Banking is one of institutions in improving the welfare. Bank is also part of the financial system and payment system of a country, even in the current globalization era, bank has also become part of the world's financial and payment systems. Bank also have a strategic role in procuring funds for economic activities by providing loan through bank credit, where bank should be confidence regarding the ability of the debtor to pay off their debts in accordance with the agreement.

Based on the prudential principle of banks in providing credit, banks pay attention to the existence of guarantees for credit. The guarantee for granting credit essentially functions to guarantee certainty of the debtor's debt repayment if the debtor is in default or declared bankrupt. The term guarantee is a translation of the Dutch language, namely *zekerheid* or *cautie*. The term collateral can be read in Article 1 number 23 of Law Number 10 of 1998 concerning Amendments to Law Number 7 of 1992 concerning Banking.

Financing disbursed by bank to debtors must be based on the agreement of the parties (Article 1 point (11) of Law No. 10 of 1998 concerning Amendments to Law No. 7 of 1992 concerning banking). However, the word "agree" is not based on pleasure or displeasure since there is an element of risk in lending. The longer the credit period, the higher the level of risk that will be faced. To minimize the risks that may arise, bank is required to apply credit principles, including asking for credit guarantees to ensure that their receivables will be returned as agreed. An agreement is an achievement where a person promises to another person or where that person promises to each other to carry out something.

Collateral is needed to guarantee the payment of a debt. Guarantee can be classified according to the laws that apply in Indonesia and those that apply abroad. Guarantee can be divided into 2 types, namely:

1. Material, namely material guarantee (both movable and immovable objects);
2. Immaterial (individual), namely individual guarantees.

With the guarantee, the bank gets certainty that the credit given can be received back at a certain time. As one of the objects of credit guarantee, land is one of the most preferred. Besides being considered the safest, the value of the land will never go down, it will even get higher in value. The guarantee referred to in this

writing is the guarantee of land rights which is included in the guarantee of immovable objects. Guarantee of land rights in the form of property rights that can be encumbered with mortgage rights as described in Article 4 Paragraph (1) of Law Number 4 of 1996 concerning Mortgage on Land and Objects Related to Land, namely: "land rights that can be encumbered with mortgage rights are: property rights; cultivation rights; building rights."

However, not all credit returns can run smoothly. There are times when the debtor is unable to carry out his obligations properly. This is certainly a legal problem, on the one hand the debtor has defaulted, on the other hand the bank/creditor also does not want to be harmed regardless of the debtor's reason. Based on the provisions referred to in Article 6 of Law Number 4 of 1996 concerning Mortgage Rights (UUHT), the creditor bank holding the first mortgage is given the right to sell the object of the mortgage on its own power through a public auction and take repayment of its receivables from the sale proceeds through an execution auction with submit an application for the implementation of the auction at the Office of the State Assets Service and Auction/KPKNL.

Of the several procedures that must be completed by the creditor before the auction is carried out, it is to determine the value of the auction limit. Based on the provisions of Article 44 paragraph (1) of the Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 27 of 2016 concerning instructions for conducting auctions, the creditor determines the limit value based on an assessment by an appraiser or an appraisal by an appraiser. Article 44 paragraph (2) states that an appraiser is a party that conducts an independent assessment based on its competence. Article 44 paragraph (3) states the definition of an appraiser, namely a party originating from the seller (creditor bank), who performs an appraisal based on a method that can be accounted for by the creditor bank, including for art objects and antique or ancient objects.

Regarding Limit Value, a new thing is regulated that the amount of the Limit Value must be determined based on the results of the assessment of the Independent Appraiser. This rule is in accordance with the provisions of the Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 27 of 2016 concerning Instructions for Auction Article 45 which in its rules only applies to the type of Non-Voluntary Execution auction with the object of the auction in the form of goods and/or buildings with a limit value of at least Rp. 1,000,000,000.00 (one billion rupiah), and Fiducia execution auction, and Bankrupt Assets Execution Auction with a Limit Value of at least Rp 1,000,000,000.00 (one billion rupiah) and/or if the creditor bank will participate as a participant in the Execution Auction Article 6 Mortgage Act or Fiducia Execution Auctions. This is reinforced by the results of research by PurnamaSianturi in 2008, that one of the characteristics of the lawsuit filed by the debtor is related to the auction price which is too low.

Based on the Jambi District Court Decision No. 31/Pdt.G/2015/PN.Jmb which adjudicated on the auction of execution of a plot of land and building which was used as collateral for mortgage, the party auctioned off the execution of the land and building (the debtor) filed a lawsuit for cancellation of the auction to the court.

That after the issuance of auction minutes, the debtor filed a lawsuit against the guarantee of land and building rights that were guaranteed. The debtor demands the cancellation of the auction minutes that have been published because they feel aggrieved by the selling value of the auction object which is considered too low. The result of the debtor's lawsuit by the panel of judges was granted that the minutes of the auction had been cancelled. In this case, the auction winner suffered a lot of losses in terms of material, energy, time and thoughts. Based on the description of the background that has been explained, this article will discuss the legal protection of the auction winner who was canceled by the court, a case study on the decision No.31/Pdt.G/2015/PN.Jmb.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research used normative juridical research. This research approach employed a statue and case approach to solve existing problems by means of deductive analysis, drawing conclusions from general to specific conditions. Collecting research data used literature studies on primary legal materials, secondary legal materials, and non-legal materials. Primary legal materials were in the form of legislation in the field of auctions and their treatises as well as legal protection. Secondary legal materials consisted of references related to the topics discussed. The data analysis technique in this research was prescriptive analysis to provide implementation and efficient outcomes.

DISCUSSION

1. Definition of auction

Auction or sale in public is a sale of goods carried out in front of the public where the price of goods offered to buyers is increasing every time. The definition of auction (public sale) is regulated in Article 1 *VenduReglement* S.1908 No.189, that auction is the sale of goods carried out in public at an

increased or decreased bid price or by entering the price in a closed envelope, or to other people. Persons who were invited or previously notified of the auction or sale, or permitted to participate, and given the opportunity to bid on closed prices. The definition of auction in general is a sale in public led by an auction official by offering a price openly or verbally, closed or in writing.

Rahmat Soemito in his book, which is quoted from Polderman, states that public sale is a tool to enter into an agreement or agreement that is most profitable for the seller by gathering interested parties. The main condition is to gather interested parties to enter into a sale and purchase agreement that is most profitable for the seller.

According to Kepmenkeu number 304/KMK.01/2002 concerning Auction Implementation Guidelines Article 1 paragraph (1) states: "Auction is the sale of goods that are open to the public either directly or through electronic media by way of offering prices verbally and/or in writing which is preceded by an effort to gather bidders". This means that currently auctions can be conducted using electronic media via the internet or online auctions.

In the Regulation of the Minister of Finance, what is meant by Auction is the sale of goods that are open to the public with a written and/or verbal price offer that is increasing or decreasing to reach the highest price preceded by the announcement of the auction. Thus, in general, there are only two requirements for general sales, namely: gathering of interested parties and providing the widest possible opportunity to submit competitive bids.

1. Auction Legal Basis

There are several special rules governing auctions, namely:

- a. *Vendu Reglement* (Auction Regulations) contained in *Staatsblaad* number 189 of 1908 as amended several times and most recently by *Staatsblaad* number 3 of 1941. *Vendu Reglement* came into force on April 1, 1908, is a regulation that regulates the basic principles of auction.
- b. *Vendu Instructie* (Auction Instructions) *Staatsblaad* number 190 of 1908 as amended several times and the last with *staatsblaad* number 85 of 1930. *Vendu Instructie* are the provisions that implement the *Vendu Reglement*.
- c. Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 106/PMK.06/2013 on the amendment to the Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 93/PMK.06/2010 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of Auctions 4. Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 160/PMK.06/2013 on the amendment of the Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 176/PMK. 06/2010 concerning Auction Center 5. Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 158/PMK.06/2013 on amendments to the Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 174/PMK.06/2010 concerning Class I Auction Officers 6. Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 159/PMK.06/2013 on the amendment to the Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 175/PMK.06/2010 concerning Class II Auction Officers. Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 27 of 2016 concerning instructions for conducting auctions. Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 213/PMK.06/2020 concerning instructions for conducting auctions.

2. Auction Function and Classification

a. Auction Function

Auctions as a means of selling goods, especially since the beginning it was intended as a public service. This means that anyone can take advantage of the services of the State Auction Unit to sell goods by auction. However, auctions actually have private and public functions. The private function of the auction lies in the essence of the auction seen from the purpose of trade, namely as a tool/means to facilitate the traffic of trade in goods. Auctions in the world of trading are basically market institutions to enter into agreements or agreements that are most beneficial to the seller. If the auction can function optimally, it is not impossible that the price formed in the auction can be a price preference. The uniqueness of the sale by auction is that in the sale the party who will enter into the agreement (the buyer) cannot be appointed beforehand.

b. Auction Classification

In terms of discussing the classification of auctions, we can equate the classification of auctions or types of auctions. The classification of auctions can be seen from the method of bidding, the type of goods being auctioned and the reason for the goods being auctioned. The discussion regarding the auction classification above is:

1) Classification of Auctions from the Method of Bidding

An auction in this way is a classification of auctions based on the method of bidding made by the auction official. This offer can be made orally or in writing. The classification of this bid is enough by saying or stating in words in front of the bidders. A written auction is an offer

made in writing. The seller or auction official has prepared the price of the goods to be auctioned to the auction participant. Bidders just offer according to the price they want.

2) **Classification of Auctions from Aspects of Objects**

An auction of this type is an auction based on the object or goods/objects to be auctioned by the auctioneer. Classification of this auction can be divided into two, namely movable and immovable objects. Movable objects are objects that can be moved or moved, such as home utensils, furniture, household furniture and others. While immovable goods are objects that cannot be moved or moved, such as land, yard land and buildings and what is stuck in the yard or glued to the building, and others.

3. Auction Cancellation

The auction minutes that have been decided should have legal force so that it can be used at a later date. However, today there are several circumstances that could invalidate the Minutes of Auction. The Minutes of Auction can be canceled by the court if elements of an unlawful act are found. In the Jambi District Court Decision Number 31/Pdt.G/2015/PN.Jmb found elements of unlawful acts. The chronology of the decision is as follows:

- a. The situation began when Misdiati, who acted as the debtor and Bank Mega, who acted as the creditor, entered into a credit agreement with the guarantee of Misdiati's land and buildings. However, at one time, Misdiati committed a default by not paying the installments that she should have done.
- b. Bank Mega as the creditor then based on Mortgage Rights registered the auction of Misdiati's land to the KPKNL for later auction of Misdiati's land.
- c. The auction process was then carried out and was won by Amrizal with the auction object being successfully sold for Rp. 191,500,000,000.00 above the limit proposed by Bank Mega worth Rp. 190,000,000.00.
- d. The selling value of Rp. 191,500,000.00 is considered by Misdiati as a value that is far below the limit because based on the applicable regulations, namely the Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 106 of 2013, the limit value is Rp. 300,000,000.00. However, Bank Mega and KPKNL only set a limit value of IDR 190,000,000.00. Where should the selling value of the auction object at that time should be Rp 500,000,000.00.
- e. This discrepancy in the selling value determined by Bank Mega and the KPKNL then became the basis for Misdiati in filing a lawsuit over the Minutes of Auction that had been carried out.

Based on the lawsuit filed by Misdiati, the Jambi District Court Decision Number 31/Pdt.G/2015/PN.Jmb is as follows:

- a. Partly granted the plaintiff's claim on behalf of Misdiati.
- b. Stating the actions of Defendant I (in this case Bank Mega) in setting the Auction Limit on Mortgage No. 2516 and the action of Defendant III (KPKNL) not applying the auction rules properly for the Mortgage, is a legal act.
- c. Declare the auction of Mortgage No. 2516 on Certificate of Ownership No. 2630 null and void.
- d. Reject the rest of the plaintiff's claims.

From the Jambi District Court Decision Number 31/Pdt.G/2015/PN.Jmb above, it is known that the auction of Mortgage No. 2516 on Certificate of Ownership No. 2630 is null and void, so the winning of the auction on behalf of Amrizal is automatically null and void.

4. Basis of Auction Cancellation

To apply for the cancellation of the auction must refer to the Regulation of the Minister of Finance (PMK) No. 27/PMK.06/2016 concerning Instructions for Implementation of Auctions. The cancellation of the auction to be carried out can only be canceled at the request of the seller or based on a stipulation or decision from a judicial institution.

Furthermore, Article 30 PMK No. 27/PMK.06/2016 explains that the cancellation of the auction prior to the auction is carried out by the Auction Officer in the event that:

- a. SKT / SKPT for the auction of goods in the form of land or land and buildings does not yet exist;
- b. Goods to be auctioned are in criminal confiscation or criminal block status from the investigating agency or public prosecutor, specifically for the Execution Auction;
- c. There is a lawsuit on the plan to implement the Article 6 UUHT Execution Auction from a party other than the debtor/executed, the husband or wife of the debtor/executed related to the ownership of the auction object;
- d. Goods to be auctioned are in the status of confiscation of guarantees or confiscation of execution or criminal confiscation, specifically for Non-execution Auctions;
- e. Does not meet the Formal Legality of the Subject and Object of the Auction;

- f. The seller cannot show or submit the original documents of ownership of the Goods to the Auction Officer;
- g. Announcement of Auction conducted by the Seller is not in accordance with the laws and regulations;
- h. *Force majeure* circumstances;
- i. There is a technical problem that cannot be resolved during the auction without the presence of the participant;
- j. The Limit Value stated in the Auction Announcement is not in accordance with the Limit Value determination letter made by the Seller; or
- k. The seller does not physically control the movable goods being auctioned.

In order to maintain legal certainty in the implementation of the auction, the cancellation of the auction after the auction has started can only be carried out by the Auction Officer in the event that:

- a. circumstances of force (*force majeure*) or *force majeure*;
- b. technical problems that cannot be resolved during the auction without the presence of the participants.

Based on the new rules, namely the Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 213/PMK.06/2020 concerning Auction Implementation Guidelines which also confirms the same as the previous Regulation PMK No. 27/PMK.06/2016 concerning Auction Implementation Guidelines for the sake of creating legal certainty, the cancellation of the auction can only be done before the auction begins.

The auction is relatively unprofitable for the debtor because the auction prioritizes paying off creditors' receivables without thinking about the selling value of the goods being auctioned, where most of the auction prices are far below the market price. In addition, debtors tend not to know what the selling price of goods is, if the selling price exceeds the debtor's debt, the excess should be returned to the debtor. This often results in auction disputes which result in difficulty for the auction winner in controlling the goods that have been paid for.

The auction winner who has obtained the minutes of the auction has the right to register his land rights at the Land Office in the context of changing the name from the old owner to the new owner. In other words, ownership rights are fully transferred to the auction winner if after the auction winner has fulfilled all the requirements of the auction, especially the payment of the price payment, as evidenced by a "sign of settlement", and upon fulfillment of the terms of the auction, the auction official issues the Minutes of Auction which is given to the buyer. by the auctioneer.

Legally, the winner of the auction has legal certainty over the auction item he bought. If there is a lawsuit by a third party to the District Court for the goods, it does not actually affect the validity of the ownership of the goods because this is based on a consideration that by selling the goods through auction means that the Auction Office as the beneficiary has guaranteed that the auctioned goods are clearly known to the owner. andand has fulfilled the requirements for auction registration because before the auction application is granted by the auction official, the auction official must verify the documents submitted by the seller/owner of the auction object.

The provisions in PMK Number 93/PMK.06/2010, namely Article 3, which states that: "Tenders that have been carried out in accordance with applicable regulations cannot be canceled".

In Article 25 of PMK Number 213/PMK.06/2020 the new regulation regarding the implementation of auctions, which also states that: "Actions that have been carried out in accordance with the provisions of the legislation, cannot be canceled". Whereas with the provisions of the rules for the implementation of the auction, the new rules and the previous rules all confirm that the auction that has been running cannot be canceled.

5. Legal Protection for Auction Winners for Minutes of Auction canceled by the Court

Basically, the issue of legal protection in terms of its source can be divided into two types, namely external legal protection and internal legal protection. The essence of internal legal protection is basically legal protection that is packaged by the parties themselves at the time of making the agreement, where when packing the contract clauses, both parties want their interests to be accommodated on the basis of an agreement. Likewise, all types of risks are endeavored to be prevented through filing of clauses that are packaged on the basis of agreement, so that with this clause the parties will obtain balanced legal protection upon their mutual consent. The parties to such internal legal protection can only be realized when their legal standing is relatively equal in the sense that the parties have relatively balanced bargaining power, so that on the basis of the principle of freedom of contract, each partner in the agreement has the freedom to express his will according to his interests. This pattern is used as the basis when the parties assemble the clauses of the agreement they are

working on, so that the legal protection of each party can be realized in a straightforward manner on their initiative.

External legal protection made by the authorities through regulations for the benefit of weak parties, “according to the nature of the laws and regulations that should not be biased and impartial, proportionally must also be given balanced legal protection as early as possible to other parties.” Because it is possible that at the beginning of the agreement, there is a party that is relatively stronger than the partner, but in the implementation of the agreement the party who was originally strong, falls into the wronged party, for example, when the debtor defaults, the creditor should also need legal protection.

The Auction Officer issues an authentic deed in the form of an Auction Minutes Deed must meet the elements of an authentic deed as regulated by Article 1868 of the Civil Code, namely “an authentic deed is a deed made in a form determined by law by or before a public official authorized for that at the place of the deed. it's made” and Article 1870 of the Civil Code, namely “for interested parties and their heirs or for people who get rights from them, an authentic deed provides a perfect proof of what is contained therein”. Minutes of Auction are made to record the agreement of the seller and buyer of the auction at the stage of the obligatory agreement. For this reason, the Auction Officer is responsible for the authenticity of the Minutes of Auction Deed.

The auction has three powers of proof as contained in the Authentic Deed, namely:

1. Minutes of Auction which has the power of outward proof. Minutes of Auction that meet the elements of an authentic deed as regulated by Articles 1868 and 1870 of the Civil Code, Minutes of Auction have three authentic elements, which are required by Article 1868 of the Civil Code, namely:
 - a. The form of the Minutes of Auction has been determined by Articles 37, 38, 39 of the VenduReglement.
 - b. Minutes of Auction are made before the Auction Officer as a General Officer in accordance with Article 1a of the Vendu Regulation.
 - c. Minutes of Auction must be made by an authorized Auction Officer in his/her territory in accordance with Article 7 of the Vendu Regulation.
2. Minutes of Auction that have the power of formal proof (formele bewijskracht). The Class II Auction Officer is responsible for making the minutes of the auction which guarantees the truth/certainty of the date of the auction, the signatures of the parties in the minutes, the identity of the people present at the auction, namely the seller, auction participant and auction buyer, as well as the place where the auction sale is held. .
3. Minutes of Auction which have the power of material proof (materialelebewijskracht). Materially, the information contained in the minutes of the auction is valid, so that if it is used as evidence before the court, it is considered sufficient and the judge is not allowed to ask for other evidence.

Other elements in Article 1868 of the Civil Code if applied in the Minutes of Auction, there is evidence that the Minutes of Auction is an Authentic Deed, namely as follows:

1. Making Minutes of Auction is carried out in front of or by the Auction Officer Le
2. The Auction Officer who makes the Minutes of Auction Deed has the authority.
3. Making the Deed he made (Class II Auction Officer is authorized to make Minutes of Auction and types of Voluntary Auctions).
4. When the deed was made (still active as Auction Officer or not).
5. Where the deed was made (related to the area of office). For whom the deed was made (for the benefit of the auction service user). Regarding the provisions of the authentic deed as a means of proof, it is contained in the law of proof (bewijsrecht) which is regulated in book IV of the Civil Code, that written evidence, especially authentic deeds and what are the requirements -The conditions are seen in Article 1869 of the Civil Code.

The authentic deed provides the parties with an absolute proof regarding the events mentioned in the deed, in proving that what is stated in the authentic deed is essentially true.

Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 27/PMK.06/2016 concerning Instructions for Implementation of Auctions contained in Article 1 number 35 which states that:

“Minutes of Auction are minutes of auction implementation made by the Auction Officer which is an authentic deed and has perfect evidentiary power”

In Article 1 number 35 it is stated that the Minutes of Auction is an authentic deed and has perfect evidentiary power for the parties.

Minutes of auction are minutes of auction implementation which have perfect evidentiary power and guarantee legal certainty of the perfect rights attached to the auction winner. The minutes of the auction are evidence that a sale and purchase agreement has been agreed between the seller of the goods and the winner of the auction. The sale-purchase agreement is one form of a named agreement,

because the sale-purchase agreement is one form of agreement that has been regulated in the Civil Code.

Judging from the chronology of the issuance of the Jambi District Court Decision Number 31/Pdt.G/2015/PN.Jmb, as well as Misdiati as the plaintiff, Amrizal as the second defendant as well as the winner of the auction bears the loss, time, energy, and funds in participating in the auction and the process transfer of name on land and taxes whose minutes of auction have been issued. With the cancellation of the published minutes of auction, Amrizal as the owner of the auction object he won will also be canceled.

In the case that happened to Amrizal, as the winner of the auction should receive legal protection in the sense that if there is a case in the auction minutes that have been published where there is an error from other parties and it ends in the cancellation of the minutes of auction by law by the court, as the winner of the auction or the buyer those who have good faith should get compensation for the losses that occur during the auction. The following are some legal grounds that can be used as protection for the auction winner for the auction minutes that the court canceled.

a. Article 1365 Civil Code

Article 1365 of the Civil Code (KUHPdata), reads: "Every act that violates the law and causes harm to others, obliges the person who caused the loss because of his mistake to replace the loss." From the sound of the article, the following elements of PMH can be drawn:

- 1) There is an unlawful act;
The unlawful act in this case, namely the auction conducted by Bank Mega was contrary to the regulations in force at that time regarding the limit value set based on the Regulation of the Minister of Finance Number 106 of 2013 amounting to Rp. limit value of IDR 190,000,000.00.
- 2) There is an error;
There was an error on the part of the perpetrator, where it was intentional because even though he knew the minimum limit value that had been determined by the Ministerial Regulation, he deliberately set a very low limit value.
- 3) There is a causal relationship between loss and action;
There is a causal relationship where the actions of Bank Mega and the KPKNL in selling the auction object below the limit value harm Misdiati, where she is entitled to receive the remainder of the debt repayment to Bank Mega from the sale of the collateral object by auction. This situation also causes losses to Amrizal because when the minutes of the auction are canceled, Amrizal's victory over the object of the auction is legally null and void.
- 4) There is a loss.
There is a loss for the victim. The actions of Bank Mega and the KPKNL caused losses to both Misdiati as the debtor and Amrizal as the winner of the auction object.

b. Article 1457 Civil Code

Sale and purchase is an agreement whereby one party binds himself to deliver an item, and the other party pays the promised price. With the sale and purchase agreement in the auction in general. Whereas the winner of the auction is the buyer, in relation to the terms of sale and purchase based on the Civil Code, the winner of the auction who is the buyer has the right to claim compensation from the seller or bidder.

c. Article 1473 Civil Code

The seller is obliged to state clearly, for what he binds himself, a promise that is not clear and can be interpreted in various meanings, must be interpreted for his loss.

d. Article 1474 Civil Code

The seller has two main obligations, namely to deliver the goods and to bear it. The auction is basically the same as buying and selling in general. That the delivery of the goods is handed over to the buyer in this case is the winner of the auction. After the payment has been made by the auction winner and has been proven to be in full and the minutes of the auction have been signed, it is the same as the sale and purchase deed which is an authentic deed because it was made before an authorized official and has fulfilled the elements of buying and selling in Article 1457 of the Civil Code.

e. Article 1479 Civil Code

Stating about the obligations of the auction seller that the guarantee that is the seller's obligation to the buyer is to guarantee two things, namely;

- 1) Control of the goods being sold is safe and peaceful;
- 2) The absence of hidden defects in the goods, or which is such as to give rise to reasons for cancellation.

It is further regulated in the provisions of Article 1480 of the Civil Code. If the delivery cannot be carried out due to the negligence of the seller, the buyer can demand the cancellation of the purchase according to the provisions of Articles 1266 and 1267.

f. Article 1266 Civil Code

Cancellation conditions are considered always included in a mutual agreement, if one of the parties does not fulfill its obligations. In such case, the agreement is not null and void, but the cancellation must be requested in court.

This request must also be made, even though the void condition regarding non-fulfillment of obligations is stated in the agreement. If the void conditions regarding the non-fulfillment of obligations are stated in the agreement, the Judge by looking at the circumstances, at the request of the defendant, is free to give a period of time to fulfill the obligations, but that period may not exceed one month.

g. Article 1267 Civil Code

The party to whom the engagement is not fulfilled, may choose; compel the other party to fulfill the agreement, if it can still be done, or demand the cancellation of the agreement, with reimbursement of costs, losses and interest.

So, based on the provisions above, that the creditor as the seller of the object being auctioned is responsible to the buyer in this case the winner of the auction in order to compensate for the loss of his rights that he has legally purchased. Whereas here the auction winner has followed the auction implementation procedure from the start of bidding and buying the auction in good faith in the buying and selling process with the creditor as the seller of the auction through the KPKNL which is carried out in a general auction. Here the winner of the auction is the buyer who is disadvantaged because he does not get his right to be able to control the auction object that has been purchased and paid off as evidenced by the publication of the Minutes of Auction. The winner of the auction from any perspective has the right to get what he should get.

CONCLUSION

The decision of the Jambi District Court Number 31/Pdt.G/2015/PN.Jmb regarding the cancellation of the Minutes of Auction with Amrizal as the winner is null and void. Minutes of auction are minutes of auction implementation which have perfect evidentiary power and guarantee legal certainty of the perfect rights attached to the auction winner. With the cancellation of the Minutes of Auction, this certainly caused losses to Amrizal as the winner of the auction because he had followed the auction process correctly, won the auction, then took care of the transfer of names and taxes at the Land Office. The losses suffered by Amrizal include losses of time, energy, and of course costs, so that the winner of the auction in this case Amrizal should receive appropriate compensation in accordance with the losses he experienced. From the events that occurred in the description above, the government should make updates regarding the legal certainty of the applicable auction regulations, especially regarding legal protection for auction winners whose auction minutes were canceled by the court. So that in the future no party will be harmed, especially the auction winner, for the canceled auction minutes.

REFERENCE

- Adrian Sutedi.(2007). *HukumPerbankanSuatuTinjauanPencucianUang, Merger, Likuidasi, danKepailatan*. Jakarta: SinarGrafika.
- Arie S. Hutagalung dalam Chadijah Rizki Lestari, 2017, *Penyelesaian Kredit Macet Bank Melalui Parate Eksekusi*, Kanun Jurnal Ilmu Hukum, Vol. 19 No. 1 April
- Ariyana Rezki Ananda, Riska Fitriani. (2016). *Pelaksanaan Lelang Terhadap Kredit Macet Pada Pt.Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Cabang Dumai*, Jom Fakultas Hukum Volume III Nomor 1, Februari.
- Callado Muñoz, F. J. (2007). The Use of Collateral in Gross and Net Payment Systems. *The European Journal of Finance*, 13(5), 459-481.
- HS Salim. (2007). *Perkembangan Hukum Jaminan di Indonesia*. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- G.H.S. Lumban Tobing (1992) , *Peraturan Jabatan Notaris*, Cetakan ketiga, Jakarta: Penerbit Erlangga
- Gregg, D. G., & Walczak, S. (2006). Auction Advisor: an agent-based online-auction decision support system. *Decision support systems*, 41(2), 449-471.

- Griffith-Jones, S., & Ocampo, J. A. (2016). Future of National Development Banks. *International Encyclopedia of Geography: People, the Earth, Environment and Technology*, 1-7.
- Konch dalam Renniwaty Siringoringo. (2012). *Karakteristik dan Fungsi Intermediasi Perbankan di Indonesia*. Buletin Ekonomi Moneter dan Perbankan. Juli.
- MiftahulRahmah. (2014). *Aspek Hukum Pelaksanaan Pelelangan Barang Tidak Bergerak Terhadap Jaminan Kredit (Studi pada PT. Bank Central Asia, TBK Cabang Lhokseumawe)*. (Skripsi, Universitas Sumatera Utara).
- Moch.Isnaeni.(2016). *Pengantar Hukum Jaminan Kebendaan*. Surabaya: PT. Revka Petra Media.
- Muhammad Djumhana dalam Yohanes Benny Apriyanto. (2017). *Penyelesaian Kredit Bermasalah Pada Bank DKI Jakarta Cabang Solo Melalui Jalur Non Litigasi*, *e-journal.uajy.ac.id/79811JURNAL.pdf*, diakses tanggal 10 November
- Purnama T. Sianturi. (2008). *Perlindungan Hukum Terhadap Pembeli Barang Jaminan Tidak Bergerak Melalui Lelang*. Bandung: CV. Mandar Maju.
- Purwahid Patrik dan Kashadi. (2001). *Hukum Jaminan Edisi Revisi dengan UUHT*. Semarang: Fakultas Hukum Universitas Diponegoro.
- Rahmat Soemitro. (1987). *Peraturan dan Instruksi Lelang*. Bandung: PT. Eresco.
- Salbiah. (2004). *Materi Pokok Pengetahuan Lelang*. Jakarta: Pusat Pendidikan dan Pelatihan Perpajakan.
- Salim HS. (2011). *Perkembangan Hukum Jaminan di Indonesia*. Jakarta: Rajawali Press.
- Subekti. (1979). *Hukum Perjanjian Cetak Keempat*. Jakarta: Intermedia.
- Sutarno. (2003). *Aspek-Aspek Hukum Perkreditan Bank*. Jakarta: CV Alfabeta.

Author Information

Nanda Fenta Saputra

Student of Master of Notary Department Universitas
Sebelas Maret Surakarta

Pujiyono

Lecturer of Master of Notary Department
Universitas Sebelas Maret Surakarta

Arief Suryono

Lecturer of Master of Notary Department
Universitas Sebelas Maret Surakarta
